

ANISOMORPHIC CONSTANT LIFE DIAGRAMS FOR A WOVEN CFRP LAMINATE AT ROOM AND HIGH TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY

A procedure for constructing the asymmetric anisomorphic constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram for composites on the basis of the static strengths in tension and compression and the reference S-N relationship at the critical stress ratio equal to the compression-tension static strength ratio, which was developed by the first author of the present article in an earlier study, is further tested on a woven fabric carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate at high temperature. By comparing the anisomorphic CFL diagrams identified for the fatigue behaviors at room temperature and 100°C, the effects of temperature on the *R*-ratio dependence of S-N relationship and on the shape of CFL diagram for the composite laminate are elucidated. It is demonstrated that the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach succeeds in adequately predicting the CFL diagrams for the woven fabric quasi-isotropic laminate at room and high temperatures, and thus the S-N relationships for different stress ratios at these different temperatures.

Keywords: CFRP, Constant Fatigue Life (CFL) Diagram, Anisomorphic CFL Diagram, Critical Stress Ratio, S-N Diagrams, High Temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

Consideration of the effect of loading mode on the sensitivity to fatigue of polymer matrix composites is of primary importance for reliable design of large-scale composite structures such as aircrafts, wind turbines in multi-megawatt range and axial flow fans in thermal power station, since the structural components in those applications are usually subjected to complex fatigue load histories characterized by changes in the amplitude, mean, frequency and waveform of stress cycling during service [1], and these mechanical factors characterizing fatigue load are well known to have significant influences on the fatigue behavior of glass and carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites.

To evaluate the effect of loading mode on the sensitivity to fatigue of composites, a large number of fatigue experiments for many different kinds of cyclic loading have to be made, which consumes considerable time and cost. From a practical point of view, therefore, it is required to develop a time- and cost-saving procedure for identifying the loading mode dependence of the fatigue strength of composites with reasonable accuracy on the basis of a limited number of tests. In practice, this can only be achieved

by means of a theoretical method for predicting the fatigue lives of composites.

For prediction of the fatigue lives of composites under various modes of loading, it is essential to establish a method for predicting the S-N curves at any stress ratios. A most effective and practical method for this purpose is to use a constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram. This traditional approach was discussed early on by Rotem [2], and a method was proposed for predicting the S-N curves of general laminates at arbitrary stress ratios on the basis of a fatigue failure envelope similar to the Goodman diagram [3]. The Goodman diagram approach, however, has not fully been justified in its predictions of the fatigue lives of unidirectional and multidirectional composites. Harris et al. [4] examined the CFL diagrams for CFRP laminates for various stress ratios and showed that the CFL envelopes are asymmetric and the peak positions are slightly offset to the right of the stress amplitude axis. Ansell et al. [5] suggested that the maxima of the CFL envelopes appear at a stress ratio almost equal to the ratio of compressive strength to tensile one. Kawai [6] and Kawai and Koizumi [7] attempted to develop a different CFL diagram approach that takes into account the gradual change in shape of CFL curves as well as the ease of material identification in terms of the mean stress sensitivity to fatigue of a composite, and proposed an efficient procedure for constructing the anisomorphic CFL diagram on the basis of the static strengths in tension and compression and the reference S-N relationship fitted to the fatigue data for the critical stress ratio. The proposed anisomorphic CFL diagram approach to prediction of S-N curves for any stress ratios was validated for the fiber-dominated fatigue behaviors of quasi-isotropic and cross-ply carbon/epoxy laminates at room temperature.

In the present study, the asymmetric anisomorphic CFL diagram approach [6, 7] to prediction of S-N relationships at arbitrary stress ratios is further tested on a woven fabric carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate at high temperature. The effect of test temperature on the shape of CFL diagram for the woven fabric quasi-isotropic laminate is also elucidated. First, constant-amplitude fatigue tests at three different stress ratios are performed at room and high temperatures in order to examine the stress ratio sensitivity in fatigue and to identify the shapes of the CFL diagrams of the woven fabric laminate at room and high temperatures. Then, the theoretical anisomorphic CFL diagrams at room and high temperatures are constructed respectively on the basis of the fatigue test data for the critical stress ratios at respective test temperatures. Additional fatigue data are obtained for two more different stress ratios, and they are used to amplify the verification of the theoretical anisomorphic CFL diagram and the evaluation of the accuracy of predictions of the S-N curves for different stress ratios.

2. MATERIALS AND TEST PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was a woven carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate $[(\pm 45), (0/90)]_{3S}$. The thickness of the laminate was about 2.4 mm. Two kinds of coupon specimens with different nominal dimension were utilized. For static tension and T-T fatigue tests in which only tensile load is applied to specimens, the long specimens based on the testing standards JIS K7073 [8] and JIS K7083 [9] were employed; the dimensions were gauge length $L_G = 100$ mm and width $W = 20$ mm. For static compression and C-C and T-C fatigue tests, on the other hand, short specimens were used to reduce a risk of buckling of specimen due to applied compressive load; the

dimensions were gauge length $L_G = 10$ mm and width $W = 10$ mm. The nominal dimensions of the short specimens were determined on the basis of the testing standards JIS K7076 [10]. For testing at room temperature, rectangular-shaped aluminum alloy tabs were glued on both ends of the specimens with epoxy adhesive (Araldite) in order to protect their gripped portions. For high temperature testing at 100°C , however, the long specimens were fatigue tested at $R = 0.1$ without tabs, since the slipping of tabs happened during fatigue testing and it was not completely avoided.

Constant amplitude fatigue tests were performed under load control at room (23°C) and high (100°C) temperatures. Fatigue load was applied to specimens in a sinusoidal waveform with a constant frequency of 10 Hz; the fatigue loading condition is based on the testing standard JIS K7083 [9]. Most specimens were fatigue tested for up to 10^6 cycles, and fatigue tests that lasted over this limited were terminated prior to fracture. In this study, fatigue tests were first performed for three kinds of stress ratios: $R = 0.1, 10, \chi$ to elucidate the effect of stress ratio on fatigue behavior. A particular value of stress ratio χ , which is called a critical stress ratio hereafter, is defined as the ratio of compressive strength σ_c (< 0) to tensile one σ_t (> 0); i.e. $\chi = \sigma_c / \sigma_t$. In order to identify the tensile and compressive strengths of the woven carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate, static tension and compression tests were performed at room (23°C) and high (100°C) temperatures prior to fatigue testing. The static tests were carried out at a constant stroke rate of 1.0%/min until the specimens fractured.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The constant amplitude fatigue test data for the woven fabric quasi-isotropic laminate at room temperature for different stress ratios $R = 0.1, 10, -0.553$ (the critical stress ratio) are shown in Fig. 1. A similar plot of the fatigue data obtained at 100°C for $R = 0.1, 10, -0.457$ are presented in Fig. 2. In these figures, the absolute values of maximum fatigue stresses are plotted against the logarithm of the number of cycles to failure, and the absolute values of static strengths are plotted as points of the ordinate in the S-N diagrams.

The effect of mean stress on S-N relationship is clearly observed. Overall, the features in mean stress sensitivity are in line with those reported so far, regardless of the test temperature. In Figs. 1 and 2, we can see that the S-N relationship is shifted downward as the stress ratio decreases from 0.1 to -0.553 at room temperature and from 0.1 to -0.457 at 100°C , respectively, indicating that a larger stress amplitude has a more deteriorating effect, and thus the sensitivity to fatigue under T-C loading becomes higher than that under T-T loading.

It is seen that the S-N relationship for C-C loading ($R = 10$) at room temperature is almost in agreement with the results for $R = -0.553$ in the high cycle range. However, the slope of the S-N relationship for $R = -0.553$ is likely to be slightly steeper than that for $R = 10$, which is consistent with the observation in the previous study and more clearly observed in Fig. 2 that shows the fatigue data at 100°C . These observations for the woven fabric quasi-isotropic laminate at room and high temperatures support that the sensitivity to fatigue is highest under cyclic loading at the critical stress ratio, regardless of the test temperature.

Fig. 1 S-N relationships at room temperature

Fig. 2 S-N relationships at high temperature

Fig. 3 shows the constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram for the woven fabric carbon/epoxy laminate at room temperature in which the alternating stress σ_a is plotted against the mean stress σ_m . Symbols in this figure correspond to given constant values of fatigue life $N_f = 10^1, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5, 10^6$. The associated maximum fatigue stress levels shown in Fig. 3 were evaluated by curve fitting to the S-N relationships for the respective stress ratios. It is clearly observed that the CFL diagram is asymmetric about the σ_a -axis, and the peak of the CFL diagram is offset rightward. The experimental CFL diagram suggests that the alternating component of fatigue stress becomes maximum at a stress ratio nearly equal to the ratio of the compressive strength to the tensile one ($R = \chi = -0.553$). The dashed straight lines in Fig. 3 were drawn by connecting the points on the radial line associated with the critical stress ratio with the tensile and compressive strength points on abscissa. It is obvious that the asymmetric linear CFL diagram cannot accurately represent the experimental CFL diagram in the range of high cycle fatigue. This fact also serves to elucidate that a theoretical CFL diagram of the Goodman type [3] based on the S-N relationship at $R = -1$ cannot always be applied with good accuracy to the fatigue life analysis of composites.

4. A THEORETICAL CONSTNAT FATIGUE LIFE DIAGRAM

The anisomorphic CFL diagram, which was developed in the previous study [6, 7], is described by means of a piecewise-defined function on the domain $[\sigma_c, \sigma_T]$. The function is prescribed by different formulae depending on the position of the mean stress σ_m .

[I] Tension dominated zone ($\sigma_m^\chi \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_T$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^\chi}{\sigma_a^\chi} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^\chi}{\sigma_T - \sigma_m^\chi} \right)^{2-\psi_\chi} \quad (1)$$

[II] Compression dominated zone ($\sigma_c \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^\chi$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^\chi}{\sigma_a^\chi} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^\chi}{\sigma_c - \sigma_m^\chi} \right)^{2-\psi_\chi} \quad (2)$$

where σ_a^χ , σ_m^χ represent the alternating and mean stress components of the maximum fatigue stresses σ_{\max}^χ for a given constant value of life N_f , and they are associated with the fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio χ . The fatigue strength ratio ψ_χ for the critical stress ratio is described as a continuous monotonic function of N_f , i.e. $\psi_\chi = f^{-1}(N_f)$, and it is determined by fitting to the reference S-N relationship for the critical stress ratio.

For the fatigue behavior at room temperature, the anisomorphic CFL diagram predicted by the proposed procedure is shown in Fig. 4 by dashed lines, together with the experimental CFL data indicated by symbols. It is seen that a good agreement between

Fig. 3 Constant fatigue life diagram at room temperature

Fig. 4 Anisomorphic CFL diagram at room temperature

the predicted and observed CFL diagrams was achieved in the tested range of fatigue life. Fig. 5 shows comparison between the predicted and experimental S-N relationships at room temperature. From Fig. 5, it is seen that the S-N curves (the solid lines) predicted for $R = 0.1$ and 10 agree well with the observed S-N relationships. The fatigue tests for different stress ratios $R = 0.5$ and -1.0 were additionally carried out at room temperature in order to further verify the proposed CFL diagram-based fatigue life prediction method. The comparison between the predicted and experimental S-N relationships for these stress ratios $R = 0.5$ and -1.0 are also shown in Fig. 5. It is seen that the S-N curves predicted by the proposed CFL diagram approach agree well with the experimental results, although there is some discrepancy between the predicted and experimental results for $R = 0.5$.

The anisomorphic CFL diagram identified for the fatigue behavior at high temperature (100°C) is shown in Fig. 6, and comparison between the experimental and predicted

Fig.5 Predicted S-N curves at room temperature

Fig. 6 Anisomorphic CFL diagram at high temperature

S-N relationships at high temperature is presented in Fig. 7. It is found that the experimental CFL diagram at 100°C is also accurately described by means of the proposed anisomorphic CFL diagram approach, and accordingly it allows accurate prediction of the S-N relationships for different stress ratios at high temperature.

Consequently, it was found that the nonlinear CFL diagram for the woven fabric carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate can be constructed by means of the anisomorphic

Fig. 7 Predicted S-N curves at high Temperature

CFL diagram approach using only the static strengths in tension and compression and the reference S-N relationship at a given temperature.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The fatigue behaviors of the woven fabric carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate $[(\pm 45), (0/90)]_{3s}$ at room and high temperatures were examined with a particular emphasis on the stress ratio sensitivity in fatigue of the material. On the basis of the fatigue data obtained at room temperature and 100°C , the validity of the fatigue life prediction method was evaluated on the basis of the fatigue behaviors at different temperatures. The experimental results showed that the constant amplitude fatigue behavior of the composite laminate has a significant sensitivity to stress ratio, regardless of the test temperature. It was also indicated that the fatigue deterioration turns most significant under fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio, regardless of the test temperature. The CFL diagrams identified at room and high temperatures were found to be nonlinear and asymmetric about the stress amplitude axis. The peaks of the CFL diagrams corresponded to the fatigue loading at the critical stress ratios for respective temperatures. The experimental CFL diagrams identified at room and high temperatures were accurately predicted by the proposed procedure. It was also confirmed that the S-N relationships predicted by the theoretical CFL diagram approach agree well with the experimental results.

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